

CSI-COP

Citizen Scientists Investigating Cookies and App GDPR compliance

Deliverable D1.8 (D7)

Data Management Plan: Initial

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Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
R	Report, DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs, DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc., OTHER: Other (Database, online tools, questionnaires, etc)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CI	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC.	

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
CS	Citizen science
DMP	Data management plan
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable
GDPR	The EU's General data protection regulation that came in to force in May 2018
IPR	Intellectual property rights
Meta-data	Anything that describes a data file, for example, the file type, file size, who authored a report with the data.

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Executive Summary

The CSI-COP project is particularly focussed on privacy-by-design. Engaging citizen scientists (CS) to investigate compliance of the general data protection regulation (GDPR), CSI-COP consortium are conscious of issues related to ethical data collection. The initial data management plan (DMP) was prepared using an online tool provided by the *Digital Curation Centre* (DCC), to comply with the EU funder's guidelines as laid out in the Horizon2020 Online manual.

This deliverable, D1.8 is the first data management document across the lifetime of the CSI-COP project. The document introduces the early data collection during CSI-COP's research phase. In this part of the project, in the first six of thirty months, CSI-COP conducted exhaustive literature review. The purpose was to learn the best practices in citizen science engagement, and to find how previous projects addressed the challenges of recruiting a diverse pool of citizen scientists reflecting the European population. The first deliverable report, D2.1 '*CS Research report. Public report on current methods in CS engagement*' has been made freely accessible through sharing on various online sites, including LinkedIn, on CSI-COP's project website, and in Pure repository. Information on D2.1 is tabulated in the Appendix of this DMP. The succeeding DMP will detail the next step in the project progressing from research to recruitment of citizen scientists, and the start of the innovation phase.

1. Introduction: data summary

The administration activities of the CSI-COP project cover the lifecycle of collected data. The consortium will manage gathered data by performing ethical collection following informed consent – making explicit what data is being collected, why, for how long, and with whom, if anyone, data is likely to be shared. CSI-COP’s living data management plan (DMP) will continually outline how the project will handle collected data both during the project duration, and after the project is completed. Moreover, the DMP will provide details on the type of data that the project will generate, whether and how these data will be exploited or made accessible for verification and re-use, and how they will be curated and preserved.

The CSI-COP project has two phases:

- i) Research, and
- ii) innovation.

As of June 2020 (project month 06), the project is in the research phase exploring best practices in wide and diverse citizen science engagement. In all phases CSI-COP will fully comply with the general data protection regulation (GDPR) in collecting and storing information. The information CSI-COP will collect is to meet the EU Horizon2020 funder’s call to find who citizen scientists are. To this end CSI-COP will collect information pertaining to anonymous data on the citizen scientists (CS) recruited for this project (gender, age-range, socio-economic group, geographical location). In the innovation phase the data CSI-COP will collect is the numbers and types of cookies in websites and in smart device apps uncovered by citizen scientists as part of their investigations

This is the first version of CSI-COP’s data management plan. Initial data collection in the CSI-COP project has the purpose to find the best practices in citizen science engagement through exhaustive literature review conducted by CSI-COP project partners.

This research is related to the main objective of the CSI-COP project: to engage citizen scientists to investigate GDPR compliance through exploring cookies in websites and in apps on smart mobile devices.

The type of data that has been collected so far is a list of publications on citizen science research. The first completed research deliverable is ‘*CS Research report. Public report on current methods in CS engagement*’ (D2.1). The size of the data realised from the literature reviewed, is spread across pages 63 to 74 in CSI-COP deliverable report D2.1 with 109 articles in a reference list, and a bibliography across pages 75 to 93 with 169 sources (Ignat et al., 2020). In the second-half of the project CSI-COP will organise workshops and an online course (MOOC), which aim to informally educate the general public about their online privacy. The next DMP will detail the data that will be collected.

The current data collected originated from a wide range of publications, including peer-reviewed articles, theses, policy reports.

The utility of this data is wide for stakeholders involved in citizen science, civic engagement, informal education and open science.

2. FAIR data

In accordance with the EU H2020 open research data pilot, CSI-COP findings will be made open under **F.A.I.R.** data management: **findable**, **accessible**, **interoperable** and **reusable**.

2.1 Making data findable

In terms of **findability** of CSI-COP project's results, reports with findings will be discoverable using a variety of avenues.

CSI-COP's first public CS report delivered at the project month M04 (April 2020) has already been shared on the project's website in 'Project Results' (csi-cop.eu). This and future CSI-COP's public reports will be made discoverable by also uploading to:

- **PURE** research information system (RIS). This online tool implements the Common European research information format (CERIF). As a repository adopted by the lead partner, Coventry University, research staff can share documents without any restrictions through their Pure profiles. The first deliverable, D2.1 has been shared and made freely accessible from first author's Pure profile (Pure, 2020);
- CERN's open science **Zenodo** platform. Zenodo provides a persistent and unique identifier through a digital object identifier (DOI) to uploaded documents. No log-in is required for people to download documents. CSI-COP first deliverable D2.1 (Ignat et al., 2020) has this DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3899478> ;
- **Academia.edu**: a platform for researchers to share their work with students and other researchers;
- **ResearchGate**: a platform for industry, academic and independent researchers to share documents;
- **LinkedIn**: a platform to enable connection to individuals, networks and reach a broad range of companies.

CSI-COP will also evaluate the efficacy of other online document repositories, such as edocr, Issuu, PDFy, General Science journal.

Social media platforms will be analysed for privacy before consideration for sharing and discoverability. Links to the project website, to Zenodo and other places where CSI-COP documents will be found, could be the most appropriate data-protection option.

Naming conventions will be contextual. The context will include the funding body (EU Horizon2020), the funding scheme (science with and for society - SwafS), entities involved in the project (lead institute, work package leaders, partners in the project), the roles in the project (as described in the project website taken from the proposal).

To optimise discoverability, project-specific tags (keywords) will be applied to CSI-COP public documents. This will be to inform on the content and improve search and retrieval of CSI-COP reports. For example, Google presents over a billion results for 'citizen science'. Over 350million results are presented in Google for 'GDPR'. CSI-COP will tag its public reports in such a way as to improve an interested party's search and increase its findability, so boost its impact.

Versioning of CSI-COP public reports will be made clear, for example on the front page of a deliverable report.

To further the success in finding CSI-COP data, in addition to unique identifiers and key search terms, the research data alliance's (RDA) meta data alliance principles will be the standard applied to CSI-COP metadata (e.g. citizen science gender, project objectives, expected impacts).

2.2 Making data openly accessible:

All data in the CSI-COP project is being made as open as possible. For example, the project website has extracted content from the EU Horizon2020 SwafS24-2019 proposal. The project's methodology, objectives, expected and additional impacts have been made open and shared on the 'About' page of CSI-COP website.

The first two deliverable reports (D1.5 list of CSI-COP events; D2.1 CS research report) are open and accessible from the 'Project Results' page on CSI-COP's website. No software is necessary to access and download these reports.

In addition to these reports, data visualisation in the form of two maps and one pie chart of the sources in D2.1 report are accessible on CSI-COP website. The data visualisation details the distribution of authors of citizen science researchers across the world, and the types of sources CSI-COP project reviewed (blogs, books, conference papers, journal papers, theses, web pages).

2.3 Making data interoperable

To make CSI-COP data **interoperable**, the project will use vocabularies relevant to the interdisciplinary nature of citizen science research into GDPR compliance. The data will be made interoperable through the creation and use of project ontologies in English and in project partner countries' languages (Greek, Hungarian, Dutch, Finnish, Hebrew, Czech, German, Catalan, Spanish).

This will allow exchange between a wide stakeholder network: citizen scientists, privacy researchers ePrivacy advocates, privacy lawyers, data protection policymakers, journalists, teachers, parents, and other organisations and institutions across Europe and beyond.

2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)

CSI-COP's data made public will be re-usable through EUDAT B2SHARE tool.

This will provide a licence to third-parties and stakeholders to use the data as it is shared in the discoverable repositories, and after the end of the project.

Assuring the quality of data during the research and innovation in CSI-COP project, data collection, data digitisation, and data checking will be conducted in steps. These steps are adapted from the UK Data Service (n.d.) and include:

- using standardised methods and protocols for capturing information alongside forms with clear instructions

- designing a purpose-built database structure to organise data and data files
- accompanying notes and documentation about the data
- peer review
- keep a single master file of data
- assign responsibility for master files to a single project team member
- regulate write access to master versions of data files
- record all changes to master files
- maintain old master files in case later ones contain errors
- archive copies of master files at regular intervals
- develop a formal procedure for the destruction of master files

The length of time for which the data could be of use and so re-usable will be 5-10 years after the conclusion of the project.

3. Allocation of resources

Cost for making CSI-COP data F.A.I.R. is part of the project management budget to maintain a living data management plan. The responsibility for data management in CSI-COP lies with all the partners led by Coventry University.

4. Data security

The types of data created, stored, and exploited throughout the project will include informal education material on informed consent in GDPR, a taxonomy of cookies – a tool with records of types of cookies on websites and in smart phone apps. Other data created will be in the form of infographics, reports, factsheets, tables, indexes, questionnaires, surveys, transcripts, photographic images and videos. All information will be stored on secure servers in the lead university, Coventry, and in CSI-COP partner-organisations. All partners have robust access controls. Coventry University IT Services ensure that the data is secure ensuring storage is mirrored to a secure ISO27001 off-campus site. Managing access to our collected data for third parties' purposes to mine, exploit, reproduce, and disseminate will be one important aspect of the project.

5. Ethical aspects

All CSI-COP project personnel will conduct ethical research and innovation. The lead partner, Coventry University, will prepare documents for ethical research approval to engage volunteer citizen scientists in the CSI-COP project. These documents will detail:

- a) the precise nature of the project,
- b) the specific purpose of citizen science engagement,
- c) the integrity of the CSI-COP researchers to act in an honest, trustworthy and timely manner with the citizen scientists at all times,
- d) the ability for citizen scientists to withdraw their volunteering at any time during the CSI-COP project and to have any collected details erased.

In addition, CSI-COP project will create an information classification system applicable to all cases to respect Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), and copyright requirements. Furthermore, the lead partner Coventry University will develop a searchable index in the system and ensure it is backed up frequently for IT Disaster Recovery purposes (Politou et al., 2018).

CSI-COP will only apply restrictions to data where it is prudent to safeguard and respect the security or confidentiality of those stakeholders/participants that the project is working with directly, to obtain sensitive information on response and operational matters. Within the Consortium Agreement, partners have stipulated clearly access rights, and IPR ownership privileges between each consortium member. In addition, CSI-COP will continually update and make CSI-COP Data Management Plan (DMP) comprehensive. The aim is to ensure managing the data management lifecycle. The project will conform to the DMP template and make every effort through communication and dissemination activities to make our content discoverable, accessible, intelligible, and usable by interested stakeholders (especially related projects). In the next, detailed data management plan we will provide clear distinction between the 'data' and how that data will be collected. CSI-COP will also detail how we determined the project's sample size, any data exclusions, manipulations, and all measures in CSI-COP scientific and technical work.

6. Other

Table 1 in the Appendix presents a data table for CSI-COP's first research report, D2.1. The table is adapted from the third author's (Stelar) data table. Data tables for subsequent CSI-COP deliverables, reports, publications tools (open access repository of cookies in websites and in apps) will detail information about each result.

References

CSI-COP website: <https://www.csi-cop.eu>

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Appendix

Brief description	Data Category	Data type	Metadata	Data format	Type of Persistent identifier	Owner	Data size	To whom outside the project data might be useful?	Publicly available?
Project deliverable	Document	Text	Authors, keywords, file type, file size	PDF	DOI (on Zenodo)	CSI-COP	1.3MB	Citizen science researchers, data management planners	Yes

Table 1: Data table for CSI-COP initial data management plan: information on deliverable research report D2.1